
An Exposition of Social Media as Tool for Development and Social Cohesion in the 21st Century

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Abstract

There are debates at various fora on national identity, peaceful and harmonious co—existence, social order and cohesion, all which are part of a broader debate that emerges from a number of apprehensions which mainly deal with identity and precisely with ethnic or religious identities versus the perceived homogeneous national identity. One of the identified fundamental challenges in immigration countries is that many migrants and ethnic minorities are not integrating into the destination or receiving societies and this creates fears about whether newcomers are developing a shared sense of belonging to the national identity or not. This study therefore created and emphasized a background on the need for maintenance of social order and cohesion without threat. The paper shortly reconceptualizes societal significance of self and social Media and how humanity peacefully can co-exists with the management of social media and shared information. It concluded with itemizing the values that the research has added to knowledge and the society.

Key Words: *Information; News Sharing; Social Media Platforms; Social Order and Cohesion*

1. Introduction and Background

Social media is broadly described as an internet space that allows people to communicate and interact with each other via user-generated content (Peng, 2017). He noted that a major reason for the attraction of social media is communication and not being able to communicate is a punishment, as evidenced by the use of solitary confinement. Thus, social media such as Facebook, Twitter, Reddit, Instagram, and WhatsApp are used by the majority of the population in many countries. According to Stieglitz and Ross (2022) social media enables users to create and share content and to participate in social networking. Mass media have also entered the digital age and play an active role on social media. Within seconds, any content can be circulated among thousands of people. This reason accounts for why Stocker, Cornforth and Green (2003) said, one impact of the introduction of television, according to widely held views, is an undermining of traditional values and social organization. However, due to the large amount of information and the variety of data sources, it has become increasingly difficult for citizens to decide on the trustworthiness of social media content. In times of global crises such as the Covid-19 pandemic in both rural and urban setting, climate change, wars, or financial crises, societies are in danger of losing stability and social cohesion (Stieglitz and Ross, 2022). The rise of fake accounts, misinformation, social bots, and hidden attempts of manipulation pose additional challenges for democratic societies. On the other hand, social media can help to foster communication among citizens and reinforce shared feelings of identity, e.g., in Europe. It can also enable citizens to communicate across borders and strengthen shared ideologies. In this thematic issue, we are publishing theoretical and empirical articles exploring social cohesion on social media from different perspectives (Stieglitz and Ross, 2022).

As Duffy and Ling (2020) submitted, people have long shared the news with each other, and technological advances make news a significant element of the information flow on social network services (SNSs) and social media. Individuals get news stories either posted there by news organisations or shared by friends and family (Holcomb, Gottfried, and Mitchell 2013) to the point that “if searching for news was the most important development of the last decade, sharing news may be among the most important of the next” (Olmstead, Mitchell, and Rosenstiel 2011, in Duffy and Ling (2020)).

In order to foster social cohesion, Sahharon, Bolong and Omar (2023) maintained that modern society depends on people's loyalty and internal convictions. In contrast to mass forums, this approach according to them seems to value people internalizing their values and beliefs as a means of achieving cohesion. In terms of social cohesion, past literatures have moved away from depending exclusively on external or group mechanisms and towards highlighting the importance of individual viewpoints, trust, and shared values in fostering cohesion within a society. It reflects the notion which is consistent with many theories of social cohesion; that social cohesion depends not only on the collective actions of individuals but also on their individual alignment with the values and norms of their society (Sahharon et al, 2023). This perspective leads us to the conclusion that social cohesion has evolved and broadened over time. The concept of social integration and collective consciousness, which emphasizes the importance of shared norms, values, and beliefs in bringing people together and laying the groundwork for society, has developed from Ibn Khaldun's early emphasis on group solidarity and unity in tribal settings to Durkheim's idea (Sahharon et al, 2023). The difficulty and network of modern society are growing as a result of massive population growth, which is driving force of this evolution. Moreover, the move to examine social cohesion at the individual level reflects the modern focus on a person's internal beliefs as a

way to promote loyalty and unity. This implies that society understands the value of individual beliefs and distinctive viewpoints in fostering social cohesion.

In summary, rapid development in the body of knowledge regarding social cohesion and social order emphasizes the dynamism of human society and how imperative it is for both individual and collective factors to shape social bonds and unity. Compared to Khaldun, Durkheim's (1893) view on cohesion is centrally concerned with the rise of modern capitalism and focused on the effects that the spread of market relations had on solidarity and on the society's ability to reproduce itself (Alexander, 2014 in Sahharon et al, 2023). His research fundamentals are concerned with how societies maintain their integrity and cohesion in modern civilization.

2. Conceptualization, Societal Significance of Self and Social Media

Social media platforms have been placed at the heart of high-profile policy discussions on how to regulate user-generated content or how to curtail information campaigns designed to steer conflict and group animosity. The societal desire for more cohesion, and policy attempts to deliver on it, often run into conflict with the goals of social media companies: many of the features that make these platforms popular, and profitable, also stoke discontent. For instance, the type of content that creates misperceptions of social norms, like outrage and incivility, is often the content that is amplified by news feed algorithms. Identifying the empirical conditions and social mechanisms that work toward social cohesion and healthy forms of political disagreement is necessary to design feasible and effective policy interventions. These can take the form of regulations (including efforts to guarantee researchers can access the data necessary to find answers of societal relevance) but also of platform design in the form of specific affordances (e.g., adding friction to the ability to share content in order to prevent the fast diffusion of misinformation (González-Bailón and Yphtach, 2023:172).

Although Durkheim emerged as one of the first thinkers in the Western tradition, along with other 19th century thinkers such as Friedrich Nietzsche, [Charles Peirce](#), and Karl Marx, rejected the Cartesian model of the self, which stipulates a transcendental, purely rational ego existing wholly independent of outside influence (IEP, 2025). In opposition to the Cartesian model, Durkheim views the self as integrated in a web of social cohesion, and thus historical, relations that greatly influence their actions, interpretations of the world, and even their abilities for logical thought. What is more, social forces can be assimilated by the individual to the point where they operate on an automatic, instinctual level, in which the individual is unaware of the effect society has on their tastes, moral inclinations, or even their perception of reality. According as put in IEP (2025), social forces thus comprise an unconscious “substructure” of the mind, in which they have to varying degrees been incorporated by the individual. In consequence, if an individual wants to know themselves, they must understand the society of which they are a part, and how this society has a direct impact on their existence. In fact, in a complete reversal of Descartes, Durkheim, following the sociological method, advocates that in order to understand one's self, the individual must avoid introspection and look outside of themselves, at the social forces that determine their personality. In these ways, Durkheim anticipated by at least fifty years the post-modern deconstruction of the self as a socio-historically determined entity (IEP, 2025).

According to González-Bailón and Yphtach (2023), the concept “social media” includes any digital platform enabling interpersonal interaction, identity signaling, and group dynamics. Social media use, time spent on social media, or specific affordances (i.e., design choices like reshare buttons or the existence of Groups and Pages) are some of the operationalizations that allow researchers to connect specific social media features to specific social cohesion outcomes. González-Bailón, et al (2023) said, social media platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and Reddit have changed how we consume and use information. These platforms decentralize content curation, allow selective exposure to like-minded sources, and offer loose moderation policies to govern interactions. Users can circumvent traditional gatekeepers of information and forge new forms of collective action. However, social media platforms have given birth to toxic, crisis and conflict-prone community, socio-political polarization, incivility, and information manipulation and mismanagement. In the past few years, social media platforms have been pushed to the spotlight of high-profile discussions that aim to identify (and, ideally, remedy) the threats these platforms currently pose to democracy (Haidt, 2022; Vaidhyathan, 2018).

From the foregoing, the significance of social unity and structure for the well-being of societies has been acknowledged since, at least, early postulation by students of social sciences and development studies pertaining social orderliness and change. As asserted by Durkheim, issues that deal with social cohesion emanate from the nonexistence of conflict and reliance on interdependence (Durkheim, 1858 – 1917). Le Bon, on the other hand, talked about crowd behavior and the antisocial tendencies individuals develop in the hold of crowds (Le Bon, 1903 [1895]). Both accounts highlight the relevance of social ties and group implant, but in one case, they are presented as a force for integration, while in the other, they are seen as a source of disorder. The conceptualization of social cohesion took its base from theoretical foundation of psychology and sociological framework. This emphasizes the relational and group dynamics that facilitate affiliations and attachments, connectedness and solidarity—but also, when absent, conflict. The psychological dimension emphasizes the attitudes, perceptions, and beliefs associated with group membership and cooperative behavior—or lack of it (González-Bailón and Yphtach (2023). In this discourse, we bring together research on these two dimensions as they converge around the common goal of explaining well-functioning communities. In the past, usual indicators of social cohesion included membership turnover, organizational commitment, attitudinal consensus, or behavioral uniformity (Friedkin, 2004 in González-Bailón and Yphtach, 2023). Interpersonal ties within and across groups (in other words, social networks) offer a theoretical mechanism to connect individual attitudes and behaviors to the group dynamics on which the label “social cohesion” is applied. Network ties facilitate information exchange which, in turn, facilitates social influence and the enforcement of norms. With the irruption of social media, relational structures, group affiliations, and behavioral dynamics have become easier to observe, measure, and analyze (Golder & Macy, 2014; Lazer et al., 2021; Lazer & Radford, 2017). Many of the patterns observed through these data do not seem aligned with the type of group dynamics we would characterize as “cohesive.”

This figure offers a schematic representation of the key concepts invoked in the literature when linking social media to social cohesion. There are several causal pathways through which platforms may alter social cohesion. For instance, they can change the structure and composition of networks, thus increasing or decreasing social capital. They can also alter individual perceptions and beliefs by changing the information realities users experience online, thus prompting different types of behavior (González-Bailón and Yphtach, 2023). Social capital and prosocial behavior are the two most common indicators of social cohesion

and they are deeply intertwined: social capital shapes individual access to resources (e.g., information) as well as opportunities for engagement and cooperation. More generally, these sociological and psychological factors are in constant interaction in the information environment social media create.

Figure 1: Theoretical Dimensions of Social Cohesion

Source: González-Bailón and Yphtach (2023).

Mcquail (1994) cited by Lewis (2008) in summarising academic debates identified a “dual perspective” on the relationship between media and social order: media are seen, in conflicting interpretations, as “centripetal,” contributing to social integration and control, or “centrifugal,” encouraging disorder or diversity. The table 1 below shows these positions by highlighting the fact that media can be seen as having a positive effect, uniting scattered individuals, integrating newcomers, providing common values, ideas and information, and helping to form identities. In contrast, the media might be viewed as provoking social dislocation, encouraging individualistic or anomic behaviour, lowering levels of social control or weakening the hold of traditional values (Lewis, 2008).

Table 1: Broadcasting and Social Cohesion

Source: McAquail (1994) in Lewis (2008).

3. Concluding Remarks

Great potential dwells in the fact that the adoption of social media reveals development and maintenance of social cohesion. This is why it is emphasized that harmonious co-existence is dependent on social cohesion's sentimental and responsive components. Cohesion is promoted and strong bonds within groups are facilitated by positive emotions, interpersonal attachments, and shared experiences which are all achieved through the social media platforms. It is recognized that these affective factors are fundamental centrifugal forces that underlies social cohesiveness. The Durkheim and other social and development theorists and theories draw attention to the complex interdependencies that exist between community members. Affective ties and cohesive behaviours within groups are largely dependent on factors like shared accountability, frequent exchanges of germane information, and structural interdependencies. It is believed that social cohesion is a necessity that creates qualitative human societal peace and tranquility. contributory network structures, categorical identifications, commitment to organisations, interpersonal attachments, and membership loyalty are all encouraged by social cohesion; as it is believed that a cohesive society is more cooperative, stable, and resilient in the face of adversity (Sahharon et al, 2023). The importance of this study from the submission of Sahharon et al, others ranges from communication literature to community development in the fact that it;

- i. Provides a chronological background and framework that studies social cohesion and order
- ii. Closes the gap in the interdisciplinary nature of social cohesion by incorporating insights from sociology, psychology, and communication theories, creating a more holistic framework for analysis.
- iii. Underscores the emotional dimensions of social cohesion, such as trust and belonging, shedding light on critical factors in understanding communication dynamics.
- iv. Enriches the field by providing historical context, interdisciplinary insights, and emotional dimensions. These contributions can provide significant benefits to researchers in communication and media studies.

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